

FEATURES AND CLINICAL MANIFESTATIONS OF COVID-19 IN CHILDREN

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Abstract. A novel coronavirus (COVID-19) has raised world concern since it emerged in Wuhan, China in December 2019. The infection may result in severe pneumonia with clusters of illness onsets. Its impacts on public health make it paramount to clarify the clinical features with other pneumonias. Community-acquired pneumonia (CAP) is a leading cause of severe infections in children, especially among the ones below the age of five, causing on a global scale the 14 % of deaths within this age group. Moreover, despite the majority of children with CAP heals, it has been estimated that complications may occur in the 3 % of CAP. Complicated community-acquired pneumonia (CCAP) include empyema, necrotizing pneumonia, and lung abscess along with systemic complications like septic shock, disseminated infection and multiorgan failure. It has been proved that viral infections (influenza, respiratory syncytial virus (RSV) and severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 (SARS-CoV-2)) constitute the primary cause of CAP and an important risk factor for CCAP in children. COVID-19 affects children less seriously than adults; however, severe cases and deaths are documented. This study objective is to determine socio-demographic, clinical and laboratory indicators associated with severe pediatric COVID-19 and mortality at hospital entrance.

Key words: Covid-19, pneumonia, pediatric, clinical and laboratory.

Introduction. Coronavirus disease 2019 (COVID-19), an infectious disease, has a substantial disease burden globally. The causative agent is the severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus type 2 (SARS-CoV-2). After the confirmation of the first case in December 2019, the disease witnessed exponential growth, with more than 768 million reported cases worldwide, culminating in a pandemic. Mortality data confirm 7 million deaths as of 2 August 2023 [1]. In the initial phase of the pandemic, COVID-19 infection was comparatively lower in children and adolescents than in the adult population in terms of both severity and frequency [2,3]. The reported cases of infections in children increased dramatically during the Omicron variant stage in early 2022, when there was relaxation in public health and social measures [4]. As the total global data on the incidence and mortality of pediatric COVID-19 cases are limited, it is challenging to assess the course and the effect of the disease in children [5,6]. Children play a pivotal role in COVID-19 transmission. Being asymptomatic, children may be responsible for the continuous spread of infection. However, a meta-analysis conducted by Chen et al. revealed that children are not actively involved in household transmission. The emergence of novel variants over time is the primary cause of increased transmissibility [7]. This study investigated the evolution of the clinical presentation of COVID-19 in children and adolescents during the course of the pandemic. Data was analysed according to the predominantly circulating severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus type 2 (SARS-CoV-2) variant and the children's age.

Material and method. Patients of the RPIATM and the Zangiota Children's Clinical Hospital were selected as the study material. Survey in July 2021 - February 2022, 75 children of different ages infected with COVID-19 were examined. In Uzbekistan, the first COVID-19 case was reported on March 15, 2020. Data from all COVID-19 pediatric cases admitted to the in April through October 2020 (first wave) was abstracted by pulmonologists and pediatricians of each hospital and independently reviewed by peer physicians at same study centers. Inclusion criteria included age less than 18 years and SARS-CoV2 infection diagnosed by RT-PCR, rapid antigen test, or rapid antibody test plus clinical suspicion of COVID-19 or need for hospital care. In addition, we have conducted scientific research on pediatric patients with Covid-19 in international scientific journals. We used Google Scholar, Pub Med, Springer Nature, and national scientific journals as international scientific journals.

Results. The COVID-19 pandemic has affected millions of people worldwide, including children. Most children experience a mild course, yet they can develop a wide range of symptoms of varying severity, including respiratory, gastrointestinal, dermatological and neurological symptoms. As the pandemic progressed, different variants of the virus emerged, including Alpha, Delta and Omicron. Numerous studies have examined the impact of these virus variants on the epidemiology and clinical presentation in adults. In children, a decreasing trend in COVID-19 severity was observed during the pandemic, but little data is available on the effect of the virus variants on the clinical presentation.

In our study, we reviewed several international retrospective studies. Clinical records were collected from patients under 18 years of age who tested positive for SARS-CoV-2 infection. Summary of the pediatric study conducted in Bolivia: The study included 209 patients. And these patients were evaluated by logistic regression, patients were admitted to intensive care units and used to determine the scientist's index. At the end of the study, 43 (20.6%) children were hospitalized in the intensive care unit and 17 (8.1%) died. Five indicators independently predicted severity of COVID-19 illness: children <10 years OR: 3.3 (CI95%: 1.1–10.4), days seeking medical care OR: 2.8 (CI95%: 1.2– 6.5), respiratory distress OR: 3.4 (CI95%: 1.4–8.2), vomiting OR: 3.3 (CI95%: 1.4–7.4), skin lesions OR: 5, 6 (CI95%: 1.9–16.6). The presence of three or more of these risk factors at hospital admission predicted severe disease in children who tested positive for COVID-19.

According to our results of the studies, the highest level of Covid-19 infection among children was observed in June-July 2021. 75 children of different ages took part in the study. Among them, it was observed that in preschool children 26.6% (20) and school-age children the disease was acute and severe in 54.6% (41), since in young and young children the disease was mild without noticeable clinical signs in 24% (14). Post-Covid syndrome in school-age children was accompanied by disturbances in the autonomic (n-15), emotional-behavioral (n-5) and cognitive spheres. Other most frequent changes in the health status of children after SARS-CoV-2 infection were identified: a 2-fold increase in episodes of acute respiratory disease in children and an exacerbation of chronic pathology of the ENT organs were noted. Symptoms of this condition ranged from mild functional impairment (n-10) to severe pathology - chronic kidney disease (n-1), pulmonary hypertension (n-2), diabetes mellitus (n-1) and which can lead to disability. (**Fig.1.**)

Lower respiratory tract infections (LRTIs) are responsible for a high level of morbidity and mortality in humans, which have been considered one of the most significant factors threatening public health worldwide [8]. The rapid spread of LRTIs-related pathogens within a short time are

frequently observed in some specific occasions (e.g., kindergarten and playground), owing to their high contagion [9]. The outbreak or occurrence of LRTIs can be caused by a variety of pathogens, including viruses, bacteria, and mycoplasma pneumoniae (MP), while the epidemiological characteristics of these infectious agents vary from regions, seasons, and other factors [10]. Thus, updating the information on the epidemiological features of LRTIs-related pathogens is essential for the early diagnosis and treatment of this disease.

Figure 1. After SARS-CoV-2 infection were identified

Another interesting scientific study is a study conducted in pediatric hospitals in Wuhan, China. According to the analysis, the main disease in 43 allergic children infected with COVID-19 was allergic rhinitis (83.7%), followed by drug allergies, atopic dermatitis, and food allergies. Food allergies and asthma have been reported. Demographic and clinical characteristics did not differ significantly between the allergic and nonallergic groups. Acute phase reactants, procalcitonin, D-dimer, and aspartate aminotransferase levels were less elevated in allergic patients compared with all patients. Immunological profiles, including numbers of circulating T, B and NK lymphocytes, total immunoglobulin and complement levels, and serum cytokines, showed no differences between the allergy and pneumonia groups. Neither eosinophil counts nor serum total immunoglobulin E (IgE) levels showed significant correlation with other immunological parameters such as other immunoglobulins, complement, lymphocyte counts and serum cytokine levels. The mean age was 6 years with a range of 3 days to 15 years, and the 182 patients studied were more likely to be male (male to female ratio approximately 2:1). Most children became infected from family members. Common symptoms were fever (43.4%) and dry cough (44.5%), with gastrointestinal manifestations such as diarrhea, abdominal discomfort and vomiting occurring in 11.0%. 71.4% had abnormal chest computed tomography (CT) images, and typical signs of pneumonia were glass opacities and patchy shadows on admission. Laboratory results were generally within normal limits, with only a small proportion of lymphopenia (3.9%) and eosinopenia (29.5%). The majority of infected children (97.8%) had a mild infection, and 24 (13.2%) were asymptomatic. Compared with children without pneumonia (asymptomatic and manifesting as an acute upper respiratory tract infection), children with a history of pneumonia had comorbidities, symptoms of fever and cough, and high levels of serum procalcitonin, alkaline phosphatase, and interleukins (ILs). -2, IL-4, IL-6, IL-10 and TNF- α . There were no differences in treatment methods, length of hospital stays, time from first positive to first negative nucleic acid test, or outcomes between children with and without pneumonia [11].

Conclusions. In conclusion, pediatric patients with COVID-19 generally have a mild clinical course, and severe cases are rare. Patients with pneumonia had higher rates of fever and cough, as

well as elevated levels of inflammatory biomarkers, than patients without pneumonia. Coronavirus infection COVID-19 leads to a decrease in the level of health and development of children, the development of multisystem diseases and a doubling of upper respiratory tract morbidity. Despite this, scientific research and pediatric research on this disease continues on a global scale.

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